

LEARNING INNOVATION BASED ON SCIENCE OF COMMUNITY SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY TO PROMOTE EARLY CHILDHOOD'S ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Ruslie, M. Thaisim¹, Eka Jayadiputra¹

¹Universitas Islam Nusantara

Abstract

The damage of nature, flood, ecological citizenship crisis, the increasingly widespread use of technology in various regions resulting in the destruction of the moral values of children, is a problem that threatens life and human life. To solve these problems the teacher has a strategic position in the functioning of his profession in order to solve the problem in the scope of learning and learning in school. Learning and learning process should take place in an interesting, open minded learner, have a sense of responsibility for the students themselves, have a better understanding and understanding of the environment, skilled in applying science in society, the ability to make decisions based on value, ability Using the science process to solve problems and make everyday decisions, concern for the value of science and technology in society, have a positive attitude toward the value of science and technology. In an effort to tackle these problems, the educational aspect with the step of applying the model of learning by the teacher is a good thing and an alternative problem solving so that embedded environmental awareness in early childhood, teachers and school life who love the environment.

Keywords: Learning Model, Society Technology Science, Environmental Awareness

Introduction

In line with the demands of development in this era of globalization, science and technology is growing very rapidly with impact almost on every aspect of human life. Among the aspects of life is the field of education, especially Early Childhood Education which is at the earliest strategic position in improving the quality of life of the nation in the future. The field of education, especially early childhood is required to be able to follow, adjust and anticipate the rapid development of science and technology so that it does not lose direction.

The above as Sutjipto in the National Convention of Education IV in Jakarta states that changes in all aspects of life in the homeland that occurred at this time caused the Indonesian nation experiencing disorientation. Therefore, education is expected to be a solid milestone for the creation of a new society of democratic Indonesia, safe, civilized, intellectual, and moral high.

Education in general aims to create a human development figure that is able to position itself as an individual and as a member of society that has the will and ability to build itself, society, nation, state and religion. This is in accordance with the function and objectives of National Education contained in Law no. 20 of 2003 on National Education System. The purpose and function of education of the heart touches the learner who has the literacy of science and technology, which contains meanings besides mastering the taught material also has attitudes and values that are useful for learners in improving the quality of life, able to use simple technology, have concern to solve the problem Which is found in everyday life and recognize and cultivate a sense of love for nature around Poedjiadi (2005).

To realize the objectives and functions of education as above, one important element in the effort to achieve the goals and functions of education in general, teacher factor and interaction and the activities of the students both in the classroom and outside the class is very important as

a form of The responsibility of educational elements through direct educational process conducted jointly between teachers, learners with learning that gives effect to the purpose and function of education that is by choosing various models that support especially instill attitude will love to environment.

One of the current student-centered learning models as well as the above educational functions is the Science-Technological-Society (S-T-S) based approach model that has become an alternative to science learning (Lien Karlina, 1995). According to this model, learning is not limited to the essential science concepts that are taught in schools, but also shows the role of science and technology in solving issues or problems that develop in society. This model is intended for the concepts of science and technology formed by learners during learning can be applied to solve problems in life (Anna Poedjiadi, 2005). The Science-Technologi-Society model is one of the teaching models concerning the application of science and technology concepts within the community.

Learning through models of Science-Technology in-Society is expected to form learner's early childhood (early childhood education) who have the benefit of early literacy to science and technology as the provision of early childhood so that they can later be alive can be harmonious and able to balance it in accordance with the development Era, so ready to absorb in applying technology in the community later in the day they mature.

Literature Review

Learning Model

The model in this case is a pattern or style of a learning process that takes place to achieve the success of a learning program. While learning is a systematic and deliberate effort to create conditions for learning activities to occur learned (Sudjana, 1993: 6). Furthermore, it is said in this learning process there has been an interaction between students who do learning activities with teachers who do research.

As is the case with Poedjiadi (2005: 119) suggests that: "a learning model is a plan, pattern or arrangement of activities of teachers and learners that shows the interaction between the elements related in learning that teachers, learners and media including teaching materials or Subject matter".

From the opinion of experts in describing the learning model, in essence that the learning model as a guide/ guidance for dipraktikan in teaching by teachers who arranged systematically in achieving learning objectives. To choose the right model, it is important to note its relevance to the achievement of teaching objectives. In practice a learning model can be said to be good if it meets the following principles: First, the smaller the teacher's efforts and the greater the student's learning activity, the better; Second, the less time teachers need to enable students to learn as well as better; Third, in accordance with the way student learning is done; Fourth, it can be done well by the teacher; Fifth, none of the most appropriate methods for all objectives, types of materials, and the existing learning process (Hasan, 1996).

Science

Etymologically the word science comes from the Latin, that is "scientia" which means knowledge. Science as a knowledge that is systematically organized in an organized sequence. Meanwhile, according to Hungerford, Volk, and Ramsey (1990), science is (1). The process of obtaining information through the empirical method (Empirical Method), (2). Information obtained through a logical and systematic investigation, and (3). A combination of critical thinking processes that produce reliable and valid information (Poedjiandji, 2005).

Science as a method of inquiry (Inquiry Methods) includes ways of thinking, attitude and steps of science activities to obtain scientific products or scientific sciences, such as observation, measurement, formulating and testing hypotheses, collecting data, experimenting and predictions. In this context, science is not just a way of working, seeing and thinking, but "Scienes as a way of knowing", meaning that science as a process can also include the tendency of attitude / action, curiosity, habitual thinking, and a set of procedures. Meanwhile, the values of science are related

to moral responsibility, social values, the benefits of science to science and human life and attitudes and actions (La Maronta Galib, 2003).

So the definition of science can be concluded, is an organized knowledge with first conducted investigations are arranged logically and systematically so as to produce information that can be trusted and valid.

Technology

Etymologically, the word technology comes from the Greek language, which consists of two syllables namely the word *techne* and *logos*. *Techne* means tips (art) or craft (craft). *Logos* means organized words or meaningful scientific discourses.

According to Indonesian dictionary, technology is a technical capability based on exact knowledge based on technical process. Fiscer (1975) provides a definition of technology as the totality of the means employed by peoples to provide material objects for human sustenance and comfort. Technology is the whole effort made by society to hold objects in order to obtain comfort and food for human self itself. Poedjiadi (2005: 18) states that technological developments start from trial and error, then the next development, starting from the 18th century technology requires the support of theory and the discovery of science to underlie its practical knowledge.

Society

Society is a picture of a social environment that has rules as the guidance of a community group in which they live together. Aikenhead (1991: 10) provides the limits of society is the social milieu. Society is a social environment, technology, social institutions, socio-cultural aspects, and the methods adopted by a community group. Ryan (1992: 59) describes the influence of science and technology on society, namely in terms of social responsibility, contribution to social decisions, social problems, the solving of practical and social problems, and contribution to economic, military, and social thinking. Society affects science and technology in matters such as fund control, policy, science activities, industry, military, ethics (in research programs), and educational institutions.

According to Ryan (Yager, 1992), the influence of science and technology on society is in terms of social responsibility, forming opinions and social problems, decision making and social action, solving practical and social problems, and contributing to economic, political development, Military, and thoughts in the field of socio-culture. On the other hand, societies can influence science and technology in terms of financial control, policy, scientific, industrial, military, moral and ethical development in research and engineering, and educational institutions.

Early Childhood Education Strategy Learning Science Technology Society

According to Poedjiadi (2005), Science of Community Technology is focused on the importance of implementing real-world context in science study, where learning can apply its knowledge to make scientific decisions related to social issues, such as environmental issues. Similarly, in early childhood learning, in addition to displaying science as a learning process, therefore, the implementation of Community Technology Science can be done with several strategies, as follows:

1. Community Technology Science is used in learning by simply connecting between science and technology concepts with the needs of society. Example: before discussing a concept, the teacher first asks whether the connection of technology and its usefulness in society.
2. Community Technology Science is used by inviting students to look for issues or issues related to the concepts to be discussed in the learning activities. The issue / issue is raised in the initial activity of the meeting and can be accompanied by the assignment of tasks that the learners must engage in outside the classroom. The task is equipped with readings and LKS that have been designed clearly.

3. Community Technology Science is used as a supplement when discussing specific concepts in line with the Teaching Program Outline (GBPP) for classes, ladder and semester or semester.

Basically, Science Technology and Society education in learning, both science and social studies, is implemented by teachers through topics discussed by connecting Science and Technology related to its use in society. The aim is to improve the motivation and achievement of learning in addition to expanding learners. In general, teachers have felt to carry out the task of teaching well, if it can lead learners menasai kinsep-concepts in the field of study that taught although not necessarily he associate the concepts of Science dengn the interests of society.

For that, there needs to be a learning model that can help Indonesian children in general to reach their future better through education. The learning model found by Anna Poedjadi is the science of technology and society (STM). The lecturer who conducted the research at the School of Chemistry and Tertiary Education Research Center of the University of New South Wales, Australia, admitted that the STM he developed first put forward John Ziman in his book, Teaching and Learning About Science Technology and Society (STS) (1980).

Technological Science Technology Learning

According to Ficher (1994: 77), provides a definition that technology is the overall effort undertaken by society in performing objects to obtain security and comfort for the human self itself.

Thus science education should reflect or lead to the relationship between Science and Technology with the society faced by humans in their daily lives.

The term STS for the first time was created by John Ziman in his book "Teaching and Learning About Science and Society" in Hidayat (2000: 25), Ziman in his book tries to express that the concepts and processes of science should be in accordance with everyday life .

The foundation of what the STS program does is to produce citizens with sufficient knowledge, to be able to make crucial decisions about current issues and issues and take action in accordance with the decisions it makes.

According to Yager (1992) said that the STS program in general has characteristics or characteristics as follows:

1. Identify local issues that have interests and impacts.
2. Use of local resources (human, fine, environment) to find information that can be used to solve problems.
3. Active participation of students in finding information that can be applied to solve problems in everyday life.
4. Extension of study outside the classroom and at school.
5. Focus on the impact of Science and Technology on students.
6. A view that isis rather than Science is not just concepts that students must master in the classroom.
7. Emphasis on the process skills that students can use in solving problems.
8. Emphasis on career awareness related to Science and Techonolgt.
9. Opportunities for students to act as citizens in which they try to resolve identified issues.
10. Identify how Science and Technology impact on the future community.
11. Freedom in learning process.

The ability of students to see and formulate problems that exist in the environment and associate it with the concept of Science is very concerned and associate it with the concept of Science. In formulating the problems will not always be based on assumptions and biases (error views).

According to Carter (2002: 275) in his article entitled "Science Technology and Access to Scientific Knowledge" says that in engaging students in the STS approach, we must be aware not

only of the social issues associated with Science, but also the values and views of society To measure the problems. For that matter it is packed in the form of solving.

According to Walter Buchingham in the book "Technology Education" (2003: 34) understanding Tecnology is a science applied into the art of industry and therefore includes tools that enable the implementation of power efficiency according to ability.

According to Poedjiadi (2005: 96) in Science Science Technologies Society of Science is the uptake of the English word Science taken from the Latin *sciencia* which means knowledge. Understanding science is limited only to positive knowledge, meaning that is only reached through our senses. In the beginning science only studies nature, but in its development also learns society.

So it can be concluded that science is a science that studies nature or natural science, and can mean science in general. So the science in this study is the science of nature.

From the above understanding can be concluded that Technology is regarded as the application of science, in the sense that the application to the deed or the embodiment of something this tendency also has a result where times Technology is considered as the application of science, dalm embodiment then dngan itself then any type of Technology or for science Knowledge can be technized. Thus the technology can not exist without being in pairs with science, and knowledge of Technology needs to be accompanied by knowledge of the science that becomes its partner.

Anna Poedjiadi (2005) in the book Society Technologies System states the development of technology starts from experimental efforts, then the next development starting from the 18th century technology requires the support of theory and the discovery of science to underlie his practical knowledge.

Technology is the answer to the problem (problem) faced by society. Technology development or the beginning of the problems faced by society, by applying the concepts of science in technology obtained the solution. According to Ryan (2002: 59) menguaraiakan influence of Science and Technology to society (society), that is in social responsibility, konteribusi to social decision, form social problem, economy, military, and social mind.

In addition, the public affects Science and Technology in terms of fund control, policy, science activities, industry, military, ethics, (in research programs), educational institutes. From the above description can be interpreted, society (society) influence and influenced by Science and Technology, thus there is interaction between Society - Science - Technology.

Ziman in The British Counal, quoted in Alit (2002: 135) classified the society into 4 groups:

1. Common people, including uneducated, non-expert and not involved in Science and Technology.
2. Society of scientists, including non-specialized educated societies, and Science science teachers.
3. Community rediator and metasain, including writers, STS scholars and educators.
4. Attentive society, including people with great interest in Science and Technology, honesty, ever known and basic education teachers.

In general, society (Society) can be defined society environment both ordinary people and scientific community. The development of Science and Technology often impact on the occurrence of social problems. This is due to the progress of Science and Technology often not balanced by the readiness of the community and continuing support of learners. Recognized also that science and Technology have positive and negative impacts, therefore people should have sufficient knowledge and understanding of the various technologies they receive.

Environmental Awareness

Concerning Robbins' (2003) awareness concept, first emphasize that for over a hundred years industry nations have witnessed the unimaginable growth of prosperity accompanied by the consumption of natural resources and other goods. The achievement of that extraordinary

prosperity has a tremendous impact on the ecosystem. Furthermore, Robbins (2003) mentions that the phenomenon of change leading to the rise of indifference to environmental sustainability. This is due to ignorance or ignorance about the existence of environmental damage.

Critical analysis of the above, according to Robbins (2003) namely, "The lack of consideration and apathy about environmental problems arises from a disconnect that has developed between humans and the land on which they live". That underlying apathy and ignorance of the environment arises from the separation of relations between human and the land in which they live. Roderick Nash's opinion, as cited by Robbins (2003) asserts that the root of the problem "which gives man dominion over his environment encourages arrogance rather than respect," that is because human beings are placed above their environment leading to arrogance rather than respect.

To address today's environmental problems, Robbins (2003) proposes the idea, "The first step in addressing our current environmental problems is to develop an environmentally-conscious society. Education is an important key towards achieving the goal of environmental awareness ". That the need to develop a society that is aware of the environment, and education is the key to achieving that goal that is environmentally conscious. The program needs to be updated, and Robbins (2003) proposes the use of "the classroom in the open" and begins to teach environmental education with a hands-on experience approach.

Environmental awareness goes from the knowledge and understanding of the natural environment as a system, and the position of man as a responsible manager. This ethical foundation confirms the need for a harmonious relationship between man and his environment. Therefore, the creation of ecological intelligence is supported by ecological conditions as well.

References

- Aikenhead, G (1991). *The Integration of STS into Science Education. Theory into Practice*, 31 (1), 27-35.
- Galib, L.M., (2003). "Pendekatan Sains-Teknologi-Masyarakat Dalam Pembelajaran Sains di Sekolah". *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan. No. 4 Tahun ke-8, Januari 2002.*: pp39-61
- I Made Mandra (2012), *Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Sains Teknologi Masyarakat (STM) terhadap Pemahaman Konsep Kimia dan Sikap Ilmiah Siswa Kelas X SMAN 1 Kediri.* *Jurnal Pendidikan Pasca Undihsa Vol.2 No.1 (2012)*
- Mareasia. (2013). *Sains, Teknologi dan Masyarakat (STM)* http://mareasia.blogspot.com/2013/07/sains-teknologi-dan-masyarakat-stm_9.html
- Poedjiadi, A. (2005). *Sains Teknologi Masyarakat*. Bandung: Rosdakarya.
- Robbins, K. (2003). *Environmental Awareness: Overcoming Ignorance and Apathy by Getting People 'Outside'*. Salt Lake City: Macalester Collage Environmental Studies Programe.
- Sudjana. (1993). *Metode dan Teknik Pembelajaran Partisipatif*. Bandung: Falah Production.
- Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang : *Sistem Pendidikan Nasional*. Jakarta : Sinar Grafika.
- Yanger, R.E. (1996). *Science Teknologi Society*. United States of Amerika. SUNY Series in Science Education.
- Yager, R.E. (1992). *Science-Technology-Society as Reform. The Status of Science-Technology-Society Reform Efforts Around the World*. ICASE Yearbook.
- Yager, R.E. 1996. *Science/Technology/Society, As Reform In Science Education*. New York: State University of New York Press.